

TRADE LIBERALIZATION AND ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES IN PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT: This research is an exertion to empirically make an assessment and confirmation about the relationship between trade advancement and environmental features in Pakistan. Time series data covering the span of 1975-76 to 2014-15 have been utilized to carry out the analysis. Trade, FDI, GDP, and taxes on trade are taken as independent variables while CO₂ emission is endogenous variables and taken as a proxy of the environment. ADF test has been used to test the order of integration. Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag Bound-testing approach is utilized to estimate the cointegration relationships. Breusch-Pagan heteroscedasticity test and Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation test are employed to test the problem of autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity. Cumulative sum of square test has been employed to check the stability of the model.

KEYWORDS - Trade Advancement, Environmental Degradation, CO₂

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's global economy, trade between countries is more rigorous and regular than in the past. Trade has become progressively imperative for global economic system. Annual trade volumes have increased sixteen fold over the last fifty years and the ratio of world exports to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is now approaching twenty percent. Trade liberalization stands for a reduction of tariff and non-tariff barriers and to step down of quotas of trade among countries. Trade liberalization enhances free trade. Trade liberalization and environment are the two main outlets describing today's political agenda (Copeland & Taylor, 2004).

With this recent acceleration of openness to trade, countries all over the world have received more investment, industrial development, employment and income growth. The benefits of trade also include the increase in consumption of goods and services that ultimately favors consumer interest. But there are some negatives of trade that includes environmental problem. The rapid increase in industrial production and urbanization is evident in the high levels of wastewater pollution, solid waste, and vehicle emissions that create serious health problems in many zones of the country. Environmental economists do not assert that international trade is bad for the economic growth of an economy but they do consider the depletion of natural resources which eventually results in damaged environment quality.

Liberalization of trade and industrialization are the main stimulants of environmental degradation. No doubt trade liberalization steers to economic growth but it also causes resource depletion and environmental degradation which in turn tend to increase the environmental cost for the community. Environmental economists believe that the real costs of the trade openness between the countries are the depletion of natural resources and environmental eminence. For long-span development, it should be ascertained that we have a decent amount of resources to compensate our next generations so that they could meet their developmental needs. If the trade is advantageous for the country, free trade should be promoted (Copeland & Taylor, 1994). Free trade is also blamed as an important reason of environmental degradation. Relaxation in trade steered by globalization has created a fresh and intriguing competition for all firms (Nolan & Zhang, 2003).

In the same manner, another study was conducted by (Chou, Melmed-Sanjak, & Shy, 1991) to inspect the consequences of trade openness on environmental degradation. When GDP increases, the larger scale of production causes more pollution and other environmental degradation problems. (Jafari,

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Farhadi, Zimmermann, & Yahoo, 2017) estimated the environmental Kuznets curve to explore the role of trade openness, FDI, the decreasing role of the state, energy consumption, and urbanization on per person CO₂ emissions in countries. This study has depicted inverted U-shaped environmental Kuznets curve (With increasing income per capita environmental cost first rises and after attaining a maximum level of environmental cost, it starts to decrease) between these variables in case of developing countries as Pakistan and India. Many other pieces of research had revealed the same relationship in context of environmental Kuznets curve for least developed economies. Pakistan trade policy to a great extent supports free trade and as a consequence, Pakistan is now facing serious environmental problems, depletion of natural resources, and significant increase in all types of pollution. There is need to improve the supply chain management according to international regulations and quality standards (Nabi, Mumtaz, & Maqsood, 2019). Positive and significant relation between trade and GDP suggested that Pakistan need to explore large economies for trade (Fatima, Nisar, & Yasmin, 2019).

Numerous studies have also been carried out to determine the impact of trade liberalization on the environment of Pakistan. The general impact of relaxing trade was adverse but there were still some heartening effects of trade on environment as scale effect and technique effect was optimistic for the economy of Pakistan. Pakistan should acutely spread a policy that pledges the investors to invest in environmentally friendly technology (Z. Ali, Zaman, & Ali, 2015). Pakistan government should not sign such agreements that risk its environment and should guarantee a decline in environmental cost associated with its industrial development (Azhar, Khalil, & Ahmed, 2007).

The impact of free trade on environment can be measured by any environmental indicator such as carbon emission, sulfur dioxide, air quality, nitrogen dioxide, pollution, etc. But this research work takes CO₂ emission as a proxy variable of the environment as CO₂ has a substantial impact on environment modification. The purpose of this research is to observe the association between CO₂, gross domestic product, foreign direct investment, trade openness, and taxes on international trade. To test the direction of causality this study has used ARDL approach.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are

- To examine whether there exist any link between trade openness and the environment.
- To recommend some policy suggestions based on study finding.

2. AN OVERVIEW OF THE EXISTING LITERATURE

This section includes a thorough study of key ideas, main issues, and theories pertinent to our research. It is a critical analysis of what others have already exposed about the problem.

(Jafari et al., 2017) estimated the environmental Kuznets curve to explore the role of trade openness, FDI liberalization, energy consumption, and urbanization on per person CO₂ emissions. To probe the research question, the data ranged from 1980-2009 was used. Variables in the model include per capita carbon emissions, GDP, FDI, trade openness, the share of govt. expenditures as percentage of GDP, per capita energy consumption, and urban population. Arellano-Bond's generalized method of moments (GMM) was used to estimate the model. The output of the results intimated that an N-shaped relationship exists between CO₂ and GDP in developed countries. While U-shaped relationship was between these variables in case of developing and least developing countries. The results also showed that FDI was not expected to decrease environmental quality. Further, energy consumption significantly affects the environmental quality and urbanization impact environmental quality only in developing countries.

(Azhar et al., 2007) made an exploration of environmental effects of trade liberalization in Pakistan. The

time series data for the Pakistan economy ranged from 1972-2001 was utilized to estimate the model. Trade openness, composition effect, scale effect, technique effect on air and water pollution were checked. Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test was applied to test stationarity. Johanson's cointegration technique was used to test long-run relationship and error correction model estimated. The results of the study revealed that in long-run there was uni-directional causation between trade liberalization and an increase in air and water pollution. The results also indicated that trade liberalization adversely affect environmental quality indicators, especially carbon emissions were increasing gradually and progressively. The study recommended that the Pakistan's government should not sign such agreements that may risk its environment. And Pakistan should assure a reduction in environmental costs associated with its industrial development.

(Awan, 2013) investigated the causation between environment and sustainable economic development. They gathered data from World Bank, IMF, Asian development bank, and relevant research journals and books. They used industrial pollution, manufacturing share in output, per capita income, total output, and manufacturing pollution intensity as variables in the model. They utilized different statistical tools such as trend and content analysis for estimation. They concluded that both developed and developing countries were responsible for environmental issues. They also concluded that the judicious use of environmental resources was a compulsory need for sustainable economic development. They advocated that environmental policies must direct poor communities. And at regional level, the countries must combine their efforts through institutional arrangements.

(Z. Ali et al., 2015) explored the effect of international trade on carbon emissions in Pakistan. The data was collected from the economic survey of Pakistan and World Bank database from 1980 to 2010. Trade openness, FDI, carbon dioxide emissions, and production technique were taken as variables and included in the model. To carry out results, the most common causality granger causality test was utilized. The results of the study depicted a bi-directional link between the production technique effect and trade openness. Findings also proposed that the production technique effect results in carbon emissions in Pakistan that in turn deteriorates the air quality. The study suggested that Pakistan should keenly devise a policy that assures the investors to invest in environmental friendly technology.

(Karsalari, Mehrara, Musai, & Mohammadi, 2014) conducted a study to determine the causality between economic growth, international trade, and the environment in case of D8 countries. The data was taken from the World Bank Indicators for the period of 1970 to 2011. Real GDP per capita, international trade, environmental quality were taken as variables for empirical analysis. To determine stationarity, panel unit root test was applied. While panel cointegration test and granger causality test were utilized to determine long-run cointegration and long-run association, respectively. The finding revealed a positive long-run association between CO₂ emissions and per capita income. The consequences also indicated a long-run relationship between CO₂ emissions and international trade.

(Grunewald, 2009) investigated the impact of the Kyoto Protocol on carbon dioxide emissions and economic growth. Data was taken from World Development Indicators. The time interval of the data was from 1960 to 2009. The study used carbon emissions, income, population, industrialization, Kyoto obligation, and financed CDM projects as variables to estimate the model. Unit root test was carried out to determine stationarity of data. OLS method was used to estimate the impact of Kyoto Protocol on carbon dioxide emissions. To resolves the problems of heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation in the error term, Driscoll-Kraay standard errors were utilized. Durbin-wu-Hausman test was also employed to test the endogeneity of Kyoto obligation. The output of the findings showed that variable Kyoto obligations had a negative and significant effect on emissions. A country with Kyoto obligation has

experienced on average 24.5 percent reduction carbon emissions as compared to a country without Kyoto obligation. They recommended that the number of countries in the Kyoto Protocol should increase, or there should be an international carbon tax on GHG emissions.

(Zafar, Anwar, Hussain, & Ahmad, 2013) probed the effects of trade liberalization and corruption on environmental degradation in Pakistan. The yearly data was collected from 1980 to 2011. Trade liberalization and corruption were taken as explanatory variables. To examine the stationarity of data, ADF test was used. ARDL model was utilized to evaluate the long-run and short-run causation between variables. Moreover, CUSUM and CUSUM square tests were applied to check the consistency of estimated model. Empirical findings suggest inverted U-shaped EKC in the case of Pakistan. The output of the study showed that industrial value added was positive and significant determinant of environmental quality. The findings also proposed that trade liberalization comport friendly environment, and corruption results support that open economies are not affected by corruption. It was suggested that Pigouvian taxes should be imposed on environmentally harmful imports.

(Mir & Storm, 2016) evaluated the carbon Kuznets curve to make a comparison between production-based and consumption-based CO₂ emissions. Data for 40 countries were collected from World Input-Output database for the period of 1995 to 2007. GDP per capita, production-based CO₂ emissions per capita, consumption-based CO₂ emissions per capita were used as variables. Fixed effect model was estimated for empirical results. The study concluded that GDP per person was not found to be a statistically significant determinant of production-based carbon emissions. The outcome of results also revealed that consumption-based GHG emissions were positively related to per capita consumption level.

(Alam, 2015) investigated the long-run association between trade liberalization, environmental degradation, and sustainable economic development in Pakistan. Time series data was used for the period of 1971 to 2008. Data was taken from World Development Indicators. Water pollution, trade liberalization, industrial GDP, fertilizer consumption, urbanization, and human development were the main variables used in the model. ADF test was used to test the stationarity. Johansen's maximum likelihood co-integration method and VAR model were utilized to carry out results. The conclusion of the study depicted that increase in urbanization, industrial, and agriculture actions were harmful for the environment while they were good for trade liberalization. The study recommended the improvement of human resource development.

(G. Ali, Ashraf, Bashir, & Cui, 2017) tried to establish the link between trade liberalization and environmental tone. The time series data covering the period of 1972 to 2006 was used for the analysis. Data was collected from WDI, Pakistan economic survey, and Pakistan energy yearbook. GDP, imports and exports, gross national capital formation, carbon dioxide emissions, labor force, and sulfur content of the fuel were the main variables of the model. To estimate the results, OLS method was used. The outcome of the study suggested that the scale effect of trade on the environment was positive but diminished while the composition effect was negative and insignificant. The study urged that there should speedy increase in GDP, an increase in the consumption of environment-friendly technology, and increase in trade openness.

(Manzoor & Samad, 2013) probed about the sustainable green growth motive of Pakistan in connection with environmental friendly technology. Green growth means effective, appropriate and desirable use of natural resources that in turn reduced environmental degradation. This study acquainted us with green growth motive of Pakistan in three spheres including IPRs, R&D expenditures, and environmental taxes. The study time period was ranged from 1960 to 2005. The outcome of the study

depicted that R&D plays an important and significant role in green growth technologies. IPRs (intellectual property rights) were weak in Pakistan and environmental taxes were regarded as good to increase green growth technologies.

After the careful examination of above literature, it can be concluded that trade liberalization and industrial development both causes environmental degradation. The above studies also show positive relationship between GDP growth and environmental degradation. As suggested by most of the studies that for achieving sustainable economic growth, countries should adopt environment friendly technologies. This study is a recent effort to explore the relationship between trade liberalization and carbon dioxide emissions with the help of updated available data.

3. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

This study used time series data to measure the impact of trade liberalization on environment in Pakistan. Data for the period of 1975 to 2015 are taken from World Development Indicators. The study used CO₂ emissions as proxy of environmental degradation while trade liberalization is measured by the sum of imports and exports. The study also used FDI, GDP and trade tariffs as control variables.

Econometric model

$$(1) \quad LCO_2 = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 LFDI + \beta_2 LTRD + \beta_3 LGDP + \beta_4 LTAXES + \mu t$$

$LCO_2 = \log$ of carbon emissions

$LFDI = \log$ of foreign direct investment

$LTRD = \log$ of trade openness

$LGDP = \log$ of gross domestic product

$LTAXES = \log$ of trade tariffs

All the variables are converted into log-form before included in the model. No doubt in smaller values there is less chances of fluctuations in the model and converting data into log-form may lead us to more accurate findings.

As time series data face the problem of non-stationary series so before estimation for the long run and short run association between variables, the need is to test for stationarity of the variables. For this purpose Augmented Dickey Fuller test is used.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Unit Root test

Prior for testing long run and short run causation between variable it is compulsory to define order of integration of all the series. For this purpose, this study has used Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test. ADF test was projected by David Dickey and Wayne Fuller in 1979. It is the simplest method to test for the unit root of series and it is monitored by Akaike Information Criterion. General ADF model is:

$$(2) \quad \Delta Y_t = \alpha_0 + \rho_1 Y_{t-1} + \alpha_2 T + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + u_t$$

The following table depicts the stationarity at both level and first difference with intercept and with both intercept and trend. The significance level is taken up as 5percent. The t-value at 5 percent is -2.93 and the value of t-calculated must be greater, in that case alternate hypothesis will be accepted.

H₀: Variable is having a unit root

H₁: Variable is not having a unit root

Table 1 Augmented Dickey-Fuller test

Variables	At level		At first difference		Conclusion
	Intercept	Trend and intercept	intercept	Trend and intercept	
CO2	-1.505509	-0.377063	-3.150548*	-7.100427*	I(1)
GDP	-4.079677*	-4.826659*	--	--	I(0)
FDI	-1.520595	-1.856960	-5.969463*	-6.262380*	I(1)
TAXES	-0.262751	-2.374350	-6.010996*	-5.945603*	I(1)
TRD	-2.105322	-2.138524	-6.400789*	-6.564670*	I(1)

*denotes the level of stationarity.

As we know that if all variables are stationary at level, we can use OLS method for estimating the relationship. Similarly, when all the variables are stationary at first difference we can use Johansen cointegration technique. In a case where some of the variables are stationary at level and some are stationary at first difference Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model is the best option. Toda-Yamamoto technique can be applied when variables of the model have order of integration at I(1) and I(2). In the current study as all the variables are integrated at first difference except GDP which is integrated at level, so this study has used ARDL model to make estimation.

Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL)

ARDL model was presented by (Pesaran, Shin, & Smith, 2001). It can be used when we have I(0) and I(1) variables. In these type of models endogenous variable depends upon the lagged value of its own as well as on the lagged values of independent variables.

In order to determine whether there exist long run relationships between variables or not, under ARDL we have used bound test. In bound test if the value of F-statistics is greater than the given upper bound, there exist the long run association between the variables.

Bound test

H₀: No cointegration exist among variables

H₁: Cointegration exist between variables

Null hypothesis will be rejected in a case when F-statistics value is greater than the upper bound values. The bound test results of this paper are given below.

Table 2 Bound test results

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	9.211693	4
Critical value bounds		
Significance	I(0) Bound	I(1) Bound
10%	2.45	3.52
5%	2.86	4.01
2.5%	3.25	4.49
1%	3.74	5.06

The results indicate that the value of F is greater than the upper bound even at 1% level of significance. So we can conclude that there exist long run relationship between environment, FDI, TRD, GDP, and TAXES.

Long run coefficient results

Table 3 Long run results of model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FDI	0.078945	0.010677	7.393845	0.0000
GDP	0.012646	0.005176	2.443025	0.0235
TAXES	-0.09614	0.001776	-5.412563	0.0000
TRD	0.013286	0.004008	3.314548	0.0033
C	-1.162428	0.182674	-6.363414	0.0000
R-squared	0.864175	Mean dependent variable		0.714205
Adjusted R-squared	0.640014	S.D. dependent variable		0.181988
S.E. of regression	0.018187	Akaike info criterion		-4.877803
Sum squared resid	0.006946	Schwarz criterion		-4.181189
Log likelihood	106.2393	Hannan-Quinn criterion		-4.632214
F-statistic	238.9254	Durbin-Watson stat		2.121297
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

The above results show that a 1 percent increase in foreign direct investment leads to 7 percent increase in carbon emissions while a 1 percent enhancement of trade advancement results in 1 percent more carbon emissions. The results are also depicting a 1 percent growth in GDP leads to 1 percent more environmental degradation. The same positive relationship between these variables was observed in case study by (Karsalari et al., 2014). They conducted a study to observe the relationship between economic growth, trade openness and environment. Taxes on trade are levied in order to restrict trade up to some extent so if there is 1 percent increase in taxes on international trade carbon emissions will diminish by 9 percent.

R-squared basically tells about how much variation in dependent variable can be explained by exogenous variables. In this model the results shows 86 percent change in dependent variable can be explained by independent variables. F-test is a valid test to estimate the entire goodness of the whole model that has a significant p-value for F-test. Durbin Watson is used to spot the problem of autocorrelation in the model and its value should always be near about to 2. The results of this study show that the value of Durbin Watson statistics is 2.12 hence we can say that there is no problem of autocorrelation in our model.

Short Run Results

In short run usually the researchers focus on the value of ECM that must be from -0 to -1. Cointegration equation basically tells us about speed of adjustment and depicts whether the model is convergent or divergent to equilibrium in long run.

The basic form of ARDL approach to cointegration testing is given below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta X_t &= \delta_{oi} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i \Delta X_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_2 \Delta Y_{t-1} + \delta_1 X_{t-1} + \delta_2 Y_{t-1} + v_{1t} \\
 \Delta Y_t &= \delta_{oi} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i \Delta Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_2 \Delta X_{t-1} + \delta_1 Y_{t-1} + \delta_2 X_{t-1} + v_{1t}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3}$$

Table 4 Short run results of study

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(FDI)	0.040047	0.010380	3.858191	0.0009
D(FDI(-1))	-0.019307	0.010616	-1.818768	0.0832
D(GDP)	0.003771	0.002271	1.660445	0.1117
D(GDP(-1))	-0.005085	0.001919	-2.649839	0.0150
D(TAXES)	0.002492	0.002188	1.138828	0.2676
D(TAXES(-1))	0.010027	0.002944	3.405753	0.0027
D(TRD)	0.002003	0.001892	1.058925	0.3017
D(TRD(-1))	0.001719	0.001817	0.945790	0.3550
D(TRD(-2))	-0.002206	0.001821	-1.211644	0.2391
D(TRD(-3))	-0.005225	0.001764	-2.961793	0.0074
cointEq(-1)	-0.820608	0.144251	-5.688739	0.0000

The above results show that the value of *ECM* is negative and significant. The value shows that the speed of convergence will be 82 percent in time period if there occurs any deviation from the equilibrium.

Residual diagnostic tests

The regression analysis can have many issues from misspecification and serial correlation to the problem of heteroscedasticity. There is no doubt that diagnostic tests are now become central topic in both econometric theory and practice. If we do not apply diagnostic tests to the model we may lead to wrong findings.

In this respect we have used different diagnostic tests such as serial correlation, heteroscedasticity, correlogram etc. In all these tests, null hypothesis will be rejected if prob-value < 0.05 and vice versa

Breusch-Godfrey Serial correlation LM test

The problem of serial correlation arises when the value of a variable is influenced by its own previous time period values. When the problem of spatial/serial correlation and heteroscedasticity exist in the model, the estimators of the model will no more be BLUE.

H₀: No serial correlation subsist.

H₁: Serial correlation does subsist.

Table 5 Serial correlation results

F-statistic	0.282832	Prob. F(2,19)	0.7568
Obs*R-squared	1.069708	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.5858

As the probability value of Chi-Square(2) is greater than 0.05 we can conclude that there is no problem of serial correlation among residuals of the model.

Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey: Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity pitfall comes into existence when the variations in different variables measured over precise time are not same. If we continue to make estimation in the presence of heteroscedasticity, whatever inference we will draw will be misleading.

H₀: No problem of heteroscedasticity exists.

H₁: Problem of heteroscedasticity does exist

Table 6 Heteroscedasticity results

Obs*R-squared	14.22917	Prob. Chi-Square(15)	0.5082
Scaled explained SS	5.271789	Prob. Chi-Square(15)	0.9896

The probability value of Chi-Square is greater than 0.05 which means that we cannot reject the null hypothesis and concluded that there is no problem of heteroscedasticity in the residuals.

Residuals Normality test

In order to determine the normal distribution of the residuals of the model that is to examine whether the random error term of current year does have any relation to past error terms or not. Histogram can be used as an efficient method to test for normality. If probability value of Jarque-Bera is larger than 0.05, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

H₀: Residuals are normally distributed.

H₁: Residuals are not normally distributed.

The probability value is 0.84 which is obviously greater than 0.05 so null is accepted concluding that residuals are normally distributed.

Stability test

These types of test are utilized to check the overall stability of the model. CUSUM OF squares test shows that our model is basically stable.

In above figure the two straight lines indicating the bound value at 5 percent level of significance. The twisted line is showing the location of model's data and it must be within the area of boundaries for the stability of the model.

5. CONCLUSION AND PROPOSITIONS

The objective of this study is to provide a glance with harmful environmental effects of trade liberalization in Pakistan. As Pakistan is a developing country, environmental friendly technology is not enhanced to that extent and the basic climate changing technologies are lacking. Therefore trade advancement inflicts negative effects on Pakistan's environment. The environmental issues are very complicated because there exists significant trade-offs between economic growth and environment. There are usually poor people who are being hurt from magnitudes of pollution and environmental degradation. The study has used carbon emissions, foreign direct investment, gross domestic products, taxes on international trade, and trade openness as variables to estimate the impact of trade liberalization on environment. For that purpose time series data for the period of 1975 to 2015 has been used. The empirical findings of study suggest a positive and significant linkage between trade openness and carbon emissions. While the effect of trade tariffs on environmental degradation is negative and significant.

The need is to encourage environmental friendly technology along with trade liberalization. This study recommended that in order to get maximum paybacks from trade liberalization the need is to introduce advanced level environmental technology so that people's health as well as Pakistan's environment remains safe. The pollution amount of exporting industries must be decrease. Awareness regarding environment in the employees of these industries can be helpful. According to estimates, the industrial sector can avoid proximately 22 percent of its total energy consumption without any loss of output if it utilizes the inputs more resourcefully.

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